

ROLE OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN EMPLOYMENT GENERATION - AN ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF UZBEKISTAN

¹Dr. Samadhi Dilli, ²Dr. Nakka Venkatarathnam, ³Dr. Somarlaraju Kishore, ⁴Dr. Cudapha
Dhanunjay Rao, ⁵Dr. K. Venkatalakshmi, ⁶Mrs. Hazratqulova Durдона Jabborovna

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259752>

***Abstract.** The present study focuses on analyzing the role of the textile industry in promoting employment opportunities in Uzbekistan. It does so by examining the increase in the number of textile production units over the study period, highlighting the industry's significant contribution to the nation's economy. A unique aspect of this study is the comparison of sector-wise employment generation, with a specific emphasis on the growth of textile manufacturing units. The study aims to identify the level of growth within the textile sector and its role in fostering productive employment in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Additionally, it attempts to analyze how the expansion of the textile industry has contributed to creating a substantial number of job opportunities over a defined period.*

***Keywords:** textile Industry Growth, Employment Improvement.*

***Ключевые слова:** рост текстильной промышленности, улучшение занятости.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** To'qimachilik sanoatining o'sishi, bandlikni yaxshilash.*

Introduction:

The textile and garment industry of Uzbekistan has undergone a significant transformation in recent years, emerging as a key player in the global textile market. Uzbekistan stands out in the global textile landscape, leveraging its distinctive strengths to become a key player in the industry. Their mission and goals revolve around elevating Uzbekistan's textile sector by bridging governmental support with private enterprise, while advancing the industry's presence on the international stage. With a history steeped in cotton cultivation dating back to the Silk Road era, Uzbekistan aims not just to be a cotton exporter but a prominent textile and resource hub in Central Asia.

The textile and clothing and knitwear industry of Uzbekistan is one of the dynamically developing sectors of the country's economy, which is largely facilitated by the presence of its own raw material base and the ever-growing demand for manufactured products. Due to its competitive potential, it occupies a leading position in attracting foreign investment when creating new enterprises, providing employment for the population, exporting products, and is also considered one of the strategically important areas in the global specialization of the country's national economy. Uzbekistan's commitment to labor reforms and international collaboration is evident in the launch of the Better Work Program by the International Labor Organization (ILO) and the International Finance Corporation (IFC). This program, initiated in June 2023, seeks to enhance working conditions and drive competitiveness in the country's key textile and garment industry.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY:

Research Gap:

There is no huge research in the analysis of Textile industry role in employment generation in Republic of Uzbekistan in the recent era of globalization compared to other nations. Hence, the present paper has a unique study in analysing the role textile industry in promoting the employment in Uzbekistan.

Need and scope of the study: The present study aims at identifying the level of employment growth through producing large number textile allied manufacturing companies and their products in Republic of Uzbekistan in general and Jizzax region in particular. An attempt is made to analyze the level of employment growth contribution in textile related products over the specified term period.

Objectives of the study:

The study has the following objectives to investigate is as follows:

- To study the growth of textile industry in Uzbekistan and Jizzax region;
- To examine the employment opportunity through production of textile products;

Data collection:

In view of the objectives of the study, secondary sources of data were used to gather the required information for in-depth investigation and analysis. The secondary data were obtained from the statistics of Uzbekistan, the statistical reports by the Department of Economics and Statistics of the Government of Uzbekistan, research studies and articles.

Period of the Study:

The study period has confined a decade from 2014 to 2024 to collect the data for detailed analysis on textile industry and its role in procuring employment development.

Tools for the study:

The collected data have been analyzed by using relevant statistical tools like Percentages, growth rates, graphs and statistical tools Standard Deviation (SD), Coefficient of Variance (CV), Anova and t-test were used for analyzing the data and drag meaningful inferences.

Limitations of the Study:

The study has its boundaries like as follows are the limitation of the study:

1. Due to time constraints, the study is limited during 2014 to 2024.
2. The data was gathered from the office of the statistics department.

Analysis on Textile Development in Uzbekistan:

A perusal of table 1 reveals textile industry growth towards registering number of textile manufacturing units in Republic of Uzbekistan during the study period.

Table 1
Development of Textile Industry in Uzbekistan
(Units in Number)

Year	Textile Manufacturing Units	Growth Rate
2015	NA	NA
2016	8,631	--
2017	10,349	0.20
2018	11,899	0.15
2019	13,540	0.14
2020	16,389	0.21
2021	18,001	0.10
2022	19,832	0.10
2023	13,040	-0.34

2024*	11,321	-0.13
Total	123002	
Average	13666.89	
SD	3701.51	

Source: Data of the Statistical Agency, Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014-2023

Note: 1. NA – Indicates Data Not Available; 2. *Indicates Data Up to July 2024

The number of Textile Manufacturing Units were registered in Republic of Uzbekistan during 2016 were 8, 631 units and it was increased year on year to 19,832 units in 2022 considerably. Hereafter, the number was declined to 11,321 units in 2024 respectively. It is observed that the number of textile manufacturing units was ranged from 8,631 units to 19,832 units over the study period.

Chart 1

It is further found that the growth rate were registered fluctuations and indexed 0.20 per cent in the base year 2017 followed by 0.15 per cent in 2018, 0.14 per cent in 2019, the highest growth 0.21 per cent during 2020. Then after it was record a decline curve 0.10 per cent in 2021 and 2022. -0.34 per cent of lowest growth was registered during the year 2023 respectively.

A glance of table 2 discloses the textile industry growth towards registering number of Textile Manufacturing Units in Jizzax Region, Republic of Uzbekistan over the study period.

Table 2

**Development of textile Industry in Jizzax Region of Uzbekistan
(Units in Number)**

Year	Textile Manufacturing Units	Growth Rate
2015	NA	NA
2016	236	--
2017	300	0.27
2018	354	0.18
2019	400	0.13
2020	545	0.36
2021	596	0.09
2022	723	0.21
2023	460	-0.36
2024*	432	-0.06

Source: Data of the Statistical Agency, Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014-2023

Note: 1. NA – Indicates Data Not Available; 2. *Indicates Data Up to July 2024

The number of Textile Manufacturing Units were registered in Jizzax Region, Republic of Uzbekistan 236 units in the year 2016 and it was continuously increased year on year to 300 units during 2017 followed by 354 units in 2018, 400 units in 2019, 545 units in 2020, 596 units in 2021, 723 units and it was declined 460 units in 2023. It is observed that the number of textile manufacturing units was ranged from 236 units to 723 units over the study period.

Chart – 2

It is further originated that the growth rate were registered fluctuations and indexed 0.27 per cent in the base year 2017 followed by 0.18 per cent in 2018, 0.13 per cent in 2019, the highest growth 0.36 per cent during 2020. Then after it was record a decline curve of 0.09 per cent in 2021, 0.21 per cent in 2022, -0.36 per cent of lowest growth was registered during the year 2023 respectively.

Employment Promotion:

A fleeting look of table 3 furnishing gender-wise employment provided in Republic of Uzbekistan by textile industry over the study period 2014 – 2023. It is found that the employment generation throughout the Uzbekistan the textile industry was registered for men ranged from 45 percent to 53 per cent in declining manner. The women employment ranged from 47 per cent to 53 per cent in increasing way year on year during the study period.

It furnished that the procurement of employment has registered in the national textile industry to women more than the men during the recent past years of the study. It is evidence that the women employment has grown from 47 per cent to 53 per cent where as the men employment number increased but the percentage declined from 53 per cent to 47 per cent over the study period.

Table 3

Dynamics of Gender-wise Employment in textile industry of Uzbekistan

Year	Men	Women	Total
	Number (%)	Number (%)	Number (%)
2014	67,564 (53.00)	59,912 (47.00)	127,480 (100)
2015	66,632 (52.70)	59,805 (48.20)	126,437 (100)
2016	69,963 (52.00)	64,581 (48.00)	134,544 (100)
2017	89,847 (51.00)	83,784 (49.00)	173,631 (100)
2018	91,748 (48.00)	96,428 (52.00)	188,176 (100)
2019	100,979 (46.00)	114,890 (54.00)	215,869 (100)
2020	99,016 (45.00)	118,897 (55.00)	217,913 (100)
2021	106,985 (45.50)	128,136 (54.50)	235,121 (100)
2022	114,767 (46.42)	132,478 (53.58)	247,245 (100)
2023	121,967 (47.00)	137,537 (53.00)	259,504 (100)
Total	929468 (100)	996448 (100)	1925920 (100)
Average	92946.80	99644.80	192592.00
SD	19699.89	30886.78	50354.85
CV	0.21	0.31	0.26
T-test	0.29		

Source: Data of the Statistical Agency, Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014-2023

Note: 1. Figures in bracket are indicates in Percentages

It is further observed that the statistical results of standard deviation (SD) were recorded for men employment 19699.89, for women employment 30886.78 and overall employment 50354.85 respectively. Hence the co-efficient of Variance (CV) were registered 0.21 for men employment, 0.31 per cent for women employment generation and overall 0.26 per cent. The t-test value recorded 0.29 per cent two sample pairs.

Chart – 3

It is a good sign that the women empowerment growing higher than the male employment in textile industry of Uzbekistan over the study period.

A deep exploration of Table 4 discloses the employment procurement of textile industry in Uzbekistan towards production of Textile products, Clothing Production and production of Leather and related products during the study period of 2014 to 2023. It is found that the total employment procurement in Textile Industry of Uzbekistan has registered as 1,925,920 people out of which, the production of Textile products are recorded 1,219,599 people followed by Clothing production were 620,738 people and Leather and other related products are 89,830 people respectively over the study period.

It is further observed that the employment of textile product production were greatly increased in increasing way, the Clothing production also constantly increased and the Leather and related products were increased in fluctuated way over the study period.

It is also reveals that the total employment of Textile industry in Uzbekistan recorded as 192,592 people were got employment, out of which textile products are highly procured employment 121,960 people followed by Clothing production 62,074 people and the least number of employment procured in Leather and related products respectively over the study period.

**Table 4
Employment Opportunities in Textile Industry of Uzbekistan**

Year	Production of Textile Products	Clothing Production	Production of Leather and Related Products	Total
2014	88,893 (69.73)	32,917 (25.82)	5,670 (4.45)	127,480 (100)
2015	87,607 (69.29)	32,489 (25.70)	6,341 (5.02)	126,437 (100)
2016	88,648 (65.89)	38,902 (28.91)	6,994 (5.20)	134,544 (100)
2017	107,530	54,835	9,335	173,631

	(61.93)	(31.58)	(5.38)	(100)
2018	115,884 (61.58)	61,833 (32.86)	10,444 (5.55)	188,176 (100)
2019	129,793 (60.13)	72,602 (33.63)	10,579 (4.90)	215,869 (100)
2020	131,290 (60.25)	74,992 (34.41)	10,198 (4.68)	217,913 (100)
2021	149,980 (63.79)	77,108 (32.80)	10,371 (4.41)	235,121 (100)
2022	161,564 (65.35)	83,892 (33.93)	9,972 (4.03)	247,245 (100)
2023	158,410 (61.04)	91,168 (35.13)	9,926 (3.82)	259,504 (100)
Total	1,219,599 (100)	620,738 (100)	89,830 (100)	1,925,920 (100)
Avg.	121,960	62,074	8,983	192,592
SD	28788.48	21450.27	1885.27	50354.85
CV	0.24	0.35	0.21	0.26
ANOVA	0.003987**			

Source: Data of the Statistical Agency, Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014-2023

Note: 1. Figures in bracket are indicates in Percentages

3. ** significant at 1 % level

The table number 4 providing the statistical results of Standard Deviation (SD), Coefficient of Variance (CV) and Analysis of Variance (Anova). The SD of total employment procurement in Uzbekistan is 50354.85, out of which Textile Industry is 28788.48, Clothing 21450.27 and Leather and related products are 1885.27 respectively. The CV of total employment procurement in Uzbekistan is 0.26 per cent, the Textile Industry is registered 0.24 per cent, Clothing 0.35 per cent and Leather and related products are 0.21 per cent respectively.

Chart - 4

The Anova value 0.003987 among the variables is very significant at 1 per cent level toward increasing the employment procurement in Republic of Uzbekistan during the study period. It is a good sign for the development of Uzbekistan Economy through procuring large number employment in Textile Industry.

A deep exploration of Table 5 expose the employment procurement of textile industry in Jizzax region of Uzbekistan towards production of Textile products, Clothing Production and production of Leather and related products during the study period of 2014 to 2023.

It is found that the total employment procurement in Textile Industry of Jizzax region, Uzbekistan registered as 78,378 people out of which, the production of Textile products are recorded 52,415 (66.87 per cent) people followed by Clothing production were 25,519 (32.56 per cent) people and Leather and other related products are 444 (0.57 per cent) people respectively over the study period.

**Table 5
Employment Opportunities in Textile Industry of Jizzax Region, Uzbekistan**

Year	Production of Textile Products	Clothing Production	Production of Leather and Related Products	Total
2014	3,291 (85.30)	540 (14.00)	27 (0.70)	3,858 (100)
2015	3,449 (81.19)	768 (18.08)	31 (0.73)	4,248 (100)
2016	3,649 (63.36)	2,057 (35.72)	53 (0.92)	5,759 (100)
2017	4,819 (61.96)	2,879 (37.01)	80 (1.03)	7,778 (100)
2018	5,087 (66.78)	2,456 (32.24)	74 (0.97)	7,617 (100)
2019	5,745 (64.18)	3,184 (35.57)	22 (0.25)	8,951 (100)
2020	7,186 (74.07)	2,490 (25.67)	25 (0.26)	9,701 (100)
2021	6,781 (66.71)	3,338 (32.84)	46 (0.45)	10,165 (100)
2022	6,550 (60.82)	4,174 (38.76)	45 (0.42)	10,769 (100)
2023	5,858 (61.46)	3,633 (38.11)	41 (0.43)	9,532 (100)
Total	52,415 (66.87)	25,519 (32.56)	444 (0.57)	78,378 (100)
Avg.	5,242	2,552	44	7,838
SD	1424.11	1174.38	19.98	2465.05
CV	0.27	0.46	0.45	0.31
ANOVA	0.024937*			

Source: Data of the Statistical Agency, Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014-2023

Note: 1. Figures in bracket are indicates in Percentages 2. * significant at 5 % level

It is further revealed that the employment procurement of Textile Industry in Jizzax during the starting year of the study period 2014 were recorded 3,858 people out of which 85.30 per cent Textile Products, 14.00 per cent Clothing Products and rest of 0.70 per cent belongs to Leather and other related products. It was largely increased to 9,532 people in 2023. Out of which, 61.46 per cent Textile Products, 38.11 per cent Clothing Products and rest of 0.43 per cent belongs to Leather and other related products.

It is further observed that the employment of textile product production in Jizzax region were significantly increased in increasing way, the Clothing production also persistently improved and the Leather and related products were enhanced in fluctuated way over the study period.

Chart – 5

It is also reveals that the total employment of Textile industry in Jizzax region of Uzbekistan recorded as 78,378 people were got employment, out of which textile products are extremely procured employment 52,415 people followed by Clothing production 25,519 people and the least number of employment procured in Leather and related products 444 respectively over the study period.

The table number 5 providing the statistical results of Standard Deviation (SD), Coefficient of Variance (CV) and Analysis of Variance (Anova). The SD of total employment procurement in Jizzax of Uzbekistan is 2465.05, out of which Textile Industry is 1424.11, Clothing 1174.38 and Leather and related products are 19.98 respectively. The CV of total employment procurement in Jizzax of Uzbekistan is 0.31 per cent, the Textile Industry is registered 0.27 per cent, Clothing 0.46 per cent and Leather and related products are 0.45 per cent correspondingly.

The Anova value 0.024937 among the variables is significant at 5 per cent level toward increasing the employment procurement in Jizzax region, Republic of Uzbekistan during the study period. It is a good indication for the development of Uzbekistan Economy through procuring large number employment in Textile Industry.

Conclusion:

This paper was concluded that the growth of number of manufacturing units largely increased consistently during last decade in Uzbekistan and in Jizzax region as well. It is a good sign to grow Uzbekistan economy through increasing the large number of textile manufacturing units with integration of technology. The textile industry of Uzbekistan has been played a predominant role in procurement of women employment higher than the men population and it is a good indication for the development of Uzbekistan Economy through procuring large number employment in Textile Industry.

REFERENCE

1. Djurabaeyev Otabek Djurabayevich, Analysis of the export activity of the textile industry of the republic of Uzbekistan, Novateur Publications, Journalnx- a Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, ISSN no: 2581 – 4230, Volume 8, Issue 12, December -2022.
2. Kadirkhodjaeva Nilufar Rakhmatullaevna, Features of developing a strategy for the textile industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, International Journal of Research Culture Society, ISSN: 2456-6683 Volume - 5, Issue - 5, May – 2021.
3. Charting the path: Uzbekistan’s textile industry evolution and global ascent December 25, 2023.
4. Dr. Sana, Yasir Jamal, The mediating role of absorptive capacity in the relationship between the dimensions of human capital and organizational performance: a conceptual framework for the textile sector of Pakistan, published in reviews of management sciences, Vol. 2 No. 2,2020.
5. Mamajanov Azizbek Alisher, et.al., Reforms in the republic of Uzbekistan regarding the development of light industry and their results, United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) report 2023.
6. USDA report, Cotton exports from Uzbekistan (code: 5201), 480lb. Bales and metric tons
7. USDA report, Cotton fabric exports from Uzbekistan, (code: 5208, 5209), square meters
8. Daryo report on president Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s discussions focused on improving Uzbekistan’s cotton production system on December 12, 2023.
9. <https://www.itmf.org/conferences/annual-conference-2024>
10. <https://kohantextilejournal.com/uzbekistans-textile-industry-conversation-uztextileprom>
<https://www.uzbekembassy.in/uzbekengilsanoat-jsc-is-liquidated-the-uzlegprom-association-is-created>

1. Associate Professor, Department of Management Studies, Sambhram University, Jizzax, Uzbekistan. E-mail ID: sdillisdilliphd@gmail.com, Ph. No. +91 99592 51724, +998 97 127 2070
2. Associate Professor and Dean, Department of Management Studies, Sambhram University, Jizzax, Uzbekistan. E-mail ID: nvrathnamphd@gmail.com, Ph. No. +91 99892 58698, +998 97 127 3050
3. Associate Professor, Annamacharya Institute of Technology and Sciences (AUTONOMOUS) (AITS), Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India. E-mail ID: kishore.somarlaraju@gmail.com, Ph. No. +91 99085 88567
4. Professor, Department of Physical Science, Navoiy state University, Navoiy, Uzbekistan.
5. Associate Professor, department of Commerce, Krishnateja Degree College, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India. E-mail ID: lakshmikvphd@gmail.com, Ph. No. +91 94919 39255
6. Student of MBA, Department of Management Studies, Sambhram University, Jizzax, Uzbekistan